

DESIGN OF SMART COMPOSITE FOR VIBRATION SUPPRESSION USING LAMINATION PARAMETERS

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Abstract

A multidisciplinary design optimization method for smart laminated composites is presented to maximize the performance of vibration suppression by the closed-loop system. The smart structure consists of a graphite-epoxy laminated plate and piezoelectric (PZT) actuators. In the optimization, design variables are lamination parameters which describe lay-up configurations of plates in the simple form, actuator placements, and weight parameters in the H_2 control system. A genetic algorithm method is employed as an optimizer. It is confirmed that results of proposed multidisciplinary design optimization technique agree well with the experimental results and the present technique effectively enhances the vibration suppression of smart composites.

1 Introduction

Vibration suppression for the fibrous composite is becoming increasingly important since it is widely used as light-weight materials for engineering structures. The light-weight structure is often operated under sever vibration environment and a smart composite with actuators and sensors is one of the effective solutions to suppress the vibration of fibrous composite.

The present study proposes a multidisciplinary optimization method for the smart composite composed of piezoelectric (PZT) actuators and graphite-epoxy materials, aiming to maximize the performance of vibration control. The objective function is H_2 performance of vibration control and design variables are actuator placements, lamination parameters which represent lay-up configurations of laminated composite, and a weighing parameter in the H_2 control systems.

The performance of vibration control strongly depends on actuator placements [1], and vibration mode shapes of structures are also important for effective control. Vibration modes of the laminated composite are affected by the fiber orientation angle in each layer, and thus the simultaneous optimization of actuator placements and fiber orientation angles is an effective method for suppression of vibration of the laminated composite. The lamination parameter is the effective technique to optimize the lay-up configurations of laminated composite plates since it describes through-thickness stiffnesses of laminated plate in the simple form. There are some methods exploiting corresponding lay-up configurations from a set of lamination parameters [2-5], and the present study employs the method using a simple genetic algorithm method proposed by Autio [3].

The smart composite is modeled by finite elements and the degree-of-freedom of model is reduced by the modal coordinate transformation technique. The vibration control system is designed by solving the H_2 control problem using a reduced-order modal model. The multidisciplinary design optimization is performed by the simple genetic algorithm method (SGA) assuming the state feedback and then the output feedback system is reconstructed based on the linear matrix inequality (LMI) approach. The experimental results validate the modeling method of the present study, and the numerical results indicate better suppression of the vibration response than plates with other lay-up configurations.

2 Analysis and optimization method

The present controlled structure is modeled by the finite elements as shown in Fig. 1. The plate dimensions are given by $a \times b \times h$, and the plate right edge is clamped. The FEA is coded by the four node rectangular element [6] based on the classical

plate theory (CPT). The element is named ACM element and has 12 degree-of-freedom as each corner of the rectangle has three variables (w , $\partial w/\partial x$ and $\partial w/\partial y$), and so in-plane deformation is not included to the degree-of-freedom. Although this element is a non-confirming element forming kinks along the boundary between elements in terms of deflection, it was confirmed that there are advantages in accuracy and calculation speed for plate bending deformation.

The bending stiffnesses of the laminated plate, D_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, \text{ and } 6$), are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} D_{11} \\ D_{22} \\ D_{12} \\ D_{66} \\ D_{16} \\ D_{26} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} U_1 & W_1 & W_2 \\ U_1 & -W_1 & W_2 \\ U_4 & 0 & -W_2 \\ U_5 & 0 & -W_2 \\ 0 & W_3/2 & W_4 \\ 0 & W_3/2 & -W_4 \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} 1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where U_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, \text{ and } 5$) are material invariants defined by material constants of the composite and W_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \text{ and } 4$) are lamination parameters defined by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} W_1 \\ W_2 \\ W_3 \\ W_4 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{24}{h^3} \int_0^{\frac{h}{2}} \begin{Bmatrix} \cos 2\theta_k \\ \cos 4\theta_k \\ \sin 2\theta_k \\ \sin 4\theta_k \end{Bmatrix} z^2 dz \quad (2)$$

where θ_k is the fiber orientation angle in the k th layer. As indicated in Eq. (1), the stiffnesses are determined only by the lamination parameters and material constants. Equation (1) does not include number of layers, and this makes it possible for lamination parameters to define the stiffnesses without number of layers. The lamination parameters are widely used as design variables for the optimization problem. However, there is a difficulty to determine the corresponding lay-up configurations or fiber orientation angles from lamination parameters. Some exploiting methods of fiber orientation angles from lamination parameters [2-5] have been presented, and, in this study, the simple genetic algorithm method (SGA) proposed by Autio [3] is employed to determine the lay-up configuration since it is simple and effective for the plate with the large number of layers.

The rectangular PZT actuators with 15 mm in width and 0.5 mm in thickness and variable values in length (the maximum length is 130 mm) are installed to appropriate positions on one side of the composite. The actuators are thin enough compared with the composite plate and effects of the mass and stiffnesses are neglected in the modeling. The actuators are therefore assumed to be attached along segments of line to input control forces at their end points.

The present optimization technique is made up of four steps as shown in Fig.2. The objective function to be minimized is the H_2 control performance with respect to the controlled response of the smart composite. Instead of assigning directly fiber orientation angles as design variables, lamination parameters are employed as the variables. The placements of PZT actuators and the weighing parameter for controlled response are also employed. The process of the present optimization is as follows.

[Step 1] Preparing the database containing natural frequencies and modal matrixes for all possible

Fig. 1. Dimensions of the present smart composite.

combinations of lamination parameters by repeatedly carrying out the finite element analysis (FEA) coded with the ACM element.

[Step 2] Assuming the state feedback $\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{F}\mathbf{q}$, performing simultaneous optimization for the lamination parameters, the PZT actuator placement and control system by the simple genetic algorithm (SGA) method. The objective function is the H_2 performance of the controlled response H_{z1} and the limitation of H_2 norm of controlled input H_u is imposed as the constraint.

[Step 3] Reconstructing the output feedback system with dynamic compensator based on the linear matrix inequality (LMI) approach.

[Step 4] Determining the fiber orientation angles from the lamination parameters by the SGA [3] again, where evaluation of objective function in the SGA process is quite simple and it is possible to calculate the fiber orientation angles corresponding to the obtained lamination parameters efficiently.

Fig.2. Flow chart of the present optimization

3 Experimental set-up

Calculated results are compared with experimental results to confirm the validity of the modeling and

controller design techniques. Figure 3 is an outline of the experimental set up.

The plate is excited by a miniature impulse hammer and the acceleration signal is measured by an accelerometer. Their placements are shown in Fig. 1. The feedback signal goes to a spectrum analyzer, and is also fed to a control PC with a control board through a low pass filter which passes a signal lower than 20 kHz. Then, the optimally designed digital controller in the control PC converts the feedback signal into the appropriate control input voltage, and the voltage amplified by a PZT driver is applied to the PZT actuators where the amplification factor is set to 30. The sampling frequency of the control system is 50 kHz.

Fig. 3. Experimental set-up.

4 Results and discussion

The material constants for the graphite-epoxy composite are: $E_1 = 80.0$ GPa, $E_2 = 8.5$ GPa, $G_{12} = 4.2$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.28$ and $\rho = 1440$ kg/m³. The plate dimensions are $a \times b \times h = 200 \times 160 \times 2.5$ mm and it is divided into $8 \times 10 = 80$ elements with 99 nodes as shown in Fig. 1. The database in Step 1 is made for all possible combinations of lamination parameters with increment 0.2 in the definition region of lamination parameters, $-1 \leq W_i \leq 1$. The lamination parameters are not independent of each other and have possible regions due to the relationships of the trigonometric functions. The possible regions are given by

$$W_1^2 + W_3^2 \leq 1$$

$$(W_2^2 - W_1^2 + W_3^2)^2 + (W_4 - 2W_1W_3)^2 \leq (1 - W_1^2 - W_3^2)^2 \quad (3)$$

Combinations of parameters in the region defined by Eq. (3) are only included in the database.

The lowest five modes are employed to the modal analysis and the lowest three modes are suppressed by the control system with the modal weight, $[1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 10^{-5} \ 10^{-5}]$. The constant weight parameter for the control input is assumed and the weight for the control performance is only searched in the optimization. The constraint on the control input is $H_u < 0.1$.

The two-point crossover and mutation are used as genetic operation with the probabilities 0.9 and 0.01, respectively. The numbers of population and generation are 2000 and 250, and five elite individuals are inherited without genetic operations at each generation shift.

Fig.4. Optimum actuator placements

Figure 4 shows obtained optimum actuator placements with two actuators which are expressed as thick bold lines. The lengths of both actuators are about 130 mm agreeing with the maximum length and both ends are placed at the clamped edge. The optimum lamination parameters obtained here are $(W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4) = (0.8, 0.8, -0.2, -0.4)$ and the corresponding fiber orientation angles for the symmetric 12-layer plate result in $[\theta_1/\theta_2/\dots/\theta_6]_s = [-15^\circ/-15^\circ/-15^\circ/45^\circ/-15^\circ/-15^\circ]_s$ where θ_1 means the angle in the outermost layer and the angles are determined by the SGA with an increment 15° in the range $-90^\circ < \theta_i \leq 90^\circ$.

Figure 5 indicates (a) calculated and (b) measured accelerances of the present plate with control and

without control. Amounts of reduction at the first, second, and third modes are 21.6, 8.30, and 0.03 dB for the calculation, and 10.8, 8.22, 0.33 dB for the experiment. Although the reduction of the first mode for the experiment is small compared with the calculation, both results agree well. This shows that the present modeling method, including neglect of the PZT mass and stiffness effects, and controller design techniques give valid results.

(a) Calculated accelerance

(b) Measured accelerance

Fig.5. Accelerance for the present smart composite system, (a) calculated and (b) measured with control and without control.

The effectiveness of the present optimization technique is validated in Table 1 by comparing obtained values of H_{z1} between the present plate and

other plates which have typical lay-up configurations, where the plates have fixed lay-up configurations but their actuator placements and control systems are obtained by the similar optimization process with the present technique. Employed plates for the comparison are orthotropic plate [0/0/0/0/0]s, cross-ply plate [0/90/0/90/0/90]s, and angle-ply plate [45/-45/45/-45/45/-45]s. The H_2 norm of the control performance H_{z1} and the control input H_u for each plate is listed in Table 1.

Table 1 The H_2 norm of control performance H_{z1} and control input H_u for each plate.

Lay-ups	$H_{z1} (\times 10^4)$	H_u
Optimum [-15/-15/-15/45/-45/-45]s	4.94	0.0945
Orthotropic [0/0/0/0/0]s	5.66	0.0987
Cross-ply [0/90/0/90/0/90]s	7.75	0.0997
Angle-ply [45/-45/45/-45/45/-45]s	18.5	0.0917

It is known that the present plate with the optimum lay-up configuration and placements of PZT actuators results in the lowest H_{z1} in the four. This validates that the present multidisciplinary design optimization technique is effective for the design of smart laminated composites to control and suppress vibration of smart structure, and it become clear that designing actuator placements and lay-up configurations or vibration mode shapes simultaneously is important.

5 Conclusions

The present study proposes a multidisciplinary design optimization method for the smart laminated composite with PZT actuators using lamination parameters to maximize the vibration control performance. Experimental results cleared the validity of the present modeling method and numerical results showed the effectiveness of the simultaneous optimization technique for both actuator placements and vibration mode shapes of smart structures.

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